

Design and Emotion Models in Practice: Discussion from a Design Workshop

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Abstract

Emotion is a rapidly growing subject of research in Design. Developing an understanding of emotion may improve user experience and allow competitive advantage for companies. Some theoretical models have been developed to explain the process in which design elicits emotions. However, few tests have been done to assess these models in the context of real design projects. Moreover, little feedback on such models has been gathered from designers.

This paper compares two models of emotion and design. The first model relates to appraisal theory. The second model divides emotions into three levels: visceral, behavioural and reflective. Designers in a practical workshop made the comparison while developing design concepts, with the goal of discussing: how valuable practising designers find literature and theories on design and emotion for applying them in their practice?

The main goal of this paper is to report feedback from designers that attempted to approach a design project by using these theoretical models.

Discussion in the workshop revealed the inherent differences between the two models: one focuses on detail; while the other offers a broader explanation of the process. The different ways in which both models classify emotions were also analysed. It is argued that in combination both models may be more useful for designers.

Findings identified by the research discuss differences between emotion and aesthetic experience, particularly at the visceral level. The designers pointed out the difference between defining the target user from marketing research, or from studying emotion. This research also discusses the benefits and drawbacks of investing time in conducting user research from an emotion perspective. Finally, the paper concludes by highlighting the importance of further research on emotion and interaction.

Keywords: industrial design, emotion models, theory and practice

I. Background

The study of emotion in design is increasingly important. Many products compete with the same technical characteristics and price. The emotions a product elicits can create a competitive advantage. Research agrees that emotion plays a primary role in purchasing decisions (Desmet, 2002). More importantly from a user perspective, products designed with specific emotions in mind can offer a better experience to their users.

Two of the main models on design and emotion are those of Norman (Norman, 2004) and Desmet (Desmet, 2002). Norman suggests *three* levels of emotions: behavioural, visceral and reflective. Desmet and Hekkert propose a model based on cognitive psychology in which the interaction between stimuli and concerns create an appraisal that results in a particular emotion (Desmet, 1999, 2000; Desmet, Hekkert, & Hillen, 2004).

Previous research has tested these models with very promising results for their use in design. Desmet's model, for instance, has been tested in design workshops to develop concepts based on the study of emotion. However, the models have not been compared to find their practical advantages and disadvantages for designing. Moreover, their authors have normally tested these models. This means that their presence in the workshops can offer first hand explanations for the designers involved. However, designers accessing the literature around these themes lack direct contact with the authors.

The main question this research attempts to address is how valuable practising designers find literature and theories on design and emotion for applying them in their practice.

This research analyses two theoretical models by using them to approach a specific design project. The research gathers feedback about the models from designers in practice.

Two groups of designers participated. Each group used their assigned theoretical model to start the research and base their concepts on that theoretical explanation. During, and at the end of the project, the designers engaged in a discussion with the researcher regarding their experience with each of the models.

I.1 Theoretical Models on Design and Emotion

There are a number of different psychology models and explanations as to how emotion is elicited. The purpose of this research is not to suggest a new model, but to report feedback from designers using models that are already part of design knowledge.

I.1.1 Desmet's Model (Appraisal Process)

Pieter Desmet's doctoral dissertation offers an analysis of different psychology theories on emotion, including bodily feedback, evolutionary, and cognitive theories (Desmet, 2002). The main advantage of cognitive theory is that it suggests explanations of internal mental states that designers might find useful for understanding the process in which emotion is elicited. In this case, the internal mental state is the appraisal process.

In the appraisal process, a person gives a judgement of *beneficial* or *harmful* to objects or events, which elicit a particular emotion. If the product were appraised as fulfilling one's concerns, this would be considered beneficial by the user and the emotion would be pleasant. If the stimulus were appraised as not fulfilling one's concerns, the emotion would be unpleasant. Psychologists suggest that this process is universal (Frijda, 1986).

Therefore, an emotion is elicited by a combination of a stimulus, and the concerns and expectations of people. For instance, if Beth buys a digital camera that fulfils her aesthetic preferences, she would feel satisfied. However, if the camera fails to offer easy access to the function she is looking for, she may feel frustrated. In this second case, the camera failed to fulfil Beth's standards of usability.

There are three general types of concerns: goals, attitudes and standards. Goals are what people want to achieve. Attitudes are people's preferences; it refers to the way people would like things to be. Standards refer to the way people believe things *should* be.

Knowledge and expectations are not concerns as such, but they function in the same way as concerns in the appraisal process. Beth might have used her boyfriend's camera before, and knows that the video recording quality is not very high in still digital cameras. However,

she is pleasantly surprised to see that her new camera has much better video quality. Figure 1 shows the main structure of the appraisal process.

Figure 1. Desmet's model. Modified from Desmet, 2002

Desmet's research focuses only on emotion elicited by the aspect of products. However, the model is developed from Frijda's appraisal process that suggests its universality.

I.1.2 Norman's Model

Norman suggests that emotion happens at three levels. The visceral level is the first instinctive reaction to a stimulus. It involves the sensory system and has no connection with a reflection of the situation. Related to design, Norman connects this level with the aspect of products and suggests it involves an aesthetic experience in which people might find things attractive. For instance, a tennis player's visceral reaction to a racquet can be elicited by the looks of the racquet.

The second level is the behavioural level. It is affected by an interaction between the product and the user. It involves the motor skills of the person and is related to the use of products. For instance, the way a tennis player emotionally perceives her racquet during a game is heavily based on the behavioural level. The power and control she commands with the new racquet may make her feel satisfied about the product.

The reflective level is affected by the product and the previous knowledge of the person; it involves a reasoning whereby to assess the situation. This can be seen as what the person 'thinks' of the object. The tennis player might prefer a new racquet for competitions (behavioural level), but also treasures and keeps an old wood racquet because of the history behind it (reflective level). Figure 2 illustrates the main structure of this model.

Figure 2. Norman's model. Modified from Norman, 2004.

The models above are not necessarily exclusive. They cover different grounds, but share a background in Cognitive Theory. The researcher decided to use these two models because of their complementary relationship to each other, thereby offering a wider, and more detailed, understanding of emotion and design. Moreover, the models chosen have already been modified from psychology to be used in design.

II. Methodology

The participants are nine fourth year industrial design students developing concepts for the Milan Furniture Fair 2006, and the researcher. The theme of the project is 'Emotion in

Mexican Customs'. The resulting products were exhibited in the Fair during April 2006. Half the students started their design project investigating emotion from Norman's theoretical perspective. The other half investigated concerns, stimuli and the resulting appraisal and emotion, from Desmet's model.

Two weeks before the workshop took place, the designers were required to read about and study their assigned model. Norman's group (NG) studied the book *Emotional Design* (Norman, 2004). Desmet's group (DG) studied some of Desmet's papers (Desmet, 1999, 2000; Desmet, Hekkert, & Hillen, 2004). The workshop started with one lecture on each model and separate discussions. The designers felt they had a comprehensive understanding of their assigned theory by the end of the workshop.

The teams started with a self-analysis of emotions. They made a list of Mexican Customs that interested them. Each participant suggested which emotion each custom made them feel. Each team categorised and analysed the customs and emotions according to their theoretical models. After the analysis, concepts were suggested in written and visual form, based on the study of emotion. Discussions took place after the first analysis and at the end of the workshop.

Designers kept working on prototypes to be exhibited in Milan after the workshop. Tables 1 and 2 show summarised examples of the analysis from NG and DG respectively.

Table 1. Example of Analysis from Desmet's Group

Customs	Emotion and Analysis	Concepts
<p>Every March 21, millions of Mexicans visit pyramids in order to celebrate the onset of spring and as a tribute to the Sun. Many of the pyramids are designed based on sun movements and on shadows cast by the sun. One of them casts a shadow on the side of the pyramid that looks like a serpent climbing.</p>	<p>Emotion: Surprise</p> <p>Appraisal: Novelty</p> <p>Knowledge and Expectation: Pyramids are static elements.</p>	<p>Lamp that detects the level of lighting in a room and behaves accordingly. It invites people to use it by surprising them.</p>
<p>Admiration and inspiration elicited in Mexicans by the Virgin of Guadalupe (Lupita). People design and make elaborated altars for the Virgin and set them outside their home or business, as a means of protection and to show respect. These altars can be found in almost every corner of the country. The designer has always been amazed at the level of admiration and respect based around Lupita in Mexico. For instance, even though Mexico City has a strong littering problem, there is hardly any rubbish to be found around altars.</p>	<p>Emotion: Admiration</p> <p>Appraisal: Legitimacy</p> <p>Concern: Legitimacy is normally motivated by the fulfilment of a standard that is not easy to achieve (Desmet, 2002, p. 138). In this case, a standard is the concern that people share. Catholicism's influence in Mexico has shaped a strong standard around Lupita.</p>	<p>The designer suggested that to elicit admiration, the previous concept (lamp) had to be manufactured to a very high standard. This brought up interesting questions that were investigated at a later point.</p>
<p>Questions from designers: Is there a way to classify emotions? Is it possible to define my target users according to concerns and not according to market characteristics? The list of 14 emotions by Desmet is too narrow for an initial analysis.</p>		

Table 2. Example of Analysis from Norman's Group

Custom	Emotion and Analysis	Concepts
<p>Traditional Cooking of Mole.</p> <p>Mole is the most traditional sauce in Mexico. It is made with up to 60 spices, many times including chilli and chocolate, and served in dozens of form, but mainly with chicken and rice. A very rough black stone mortar is used to grind the spices together. The designer was fascinated by the texture of the mortar. He always felt curiosity to know what dish was going to be made every time he saw the texture of the mortar. The texture of the mortar was also used to give a specific texture to the mole.</p>	<p>Behavioural Level.</p> <p>Emotions: Curiosity, fascination.</p> <p>Textures suggest meaning and offer different sensations. Textures also suggest particular use and thus open the doors for particular behaviour.</p> <p>People may be affected at their behavioural level when engaged with textures.</p>	<p>Sofa with different textures on the surface. Each texture suggests a particular interaction and sparks user curiosity, inviting him or her to explore the object. For instance, in part of the sofa the user can sink into and be cuddled by a particular texture.</p>
<p>Experience around the boats in the canals of Xochimilco, Mexico City.</p> <p>These boats (chinampas) have a flat base with a roof decorated with colourful flowers. Each chinampa has a name written in flowers at the front of the roof. The chinampas are moved by a rower with a long wooden stick that reaches the bottom of the canals. Young Mexicans have recently adopted the canals as a place to party in the weekends.</p>	<p>Visceral level: attraction to the flower ornaments on the chinampas, and the design of the boats.</p> <p>Behavioural level: the experience of spending some hours navigating the canals, and steering the boat.</p> <p>Reflective level: satisfaction from having a natural and traditional setting within polluted Mexico City; and disappointment because of the many teenagers using the place to drink and party.</p>	<p>This framework helped classify the emotions, but it did not offer deeper analysis to develop concepts.</p>
<p>Questions from students: Is there a list of emotions we can start the analysis from? If the same object produces different emotions in different people, what produces the emotion? How can I use that information for designing?</p>		

III. Results and Discussion

Designers raised several questions during the first discussion. In order to address a practical project based on the theoretical models, they were interested in: What classification of emotions designers can use, and in which circumstances? How can the model help us address aesthetic issues? Can we define target users based on emotion? The debate surrounding these issues brought up four points that are shown below.

III. 1 Categories of Emotion

DG realised that categorising the emotions they had gathered on visceral, behavioural and reflective levels, could help them achieve a more relevant order. One example is the study of the Virgin of Guadalupe. At the visceral level, the *appearance* of the altars on the street and in churches was included. In the behavioural level the designer included the *activities* that happen around the fixed altars. The religious, social, and historical *meaning* of the Virgin was included at the reflective level.

On the other hand, NG had studied the emotions they wanted to elicit on the three different levels. However, they had not searched for factors that might have elicited these emotions. They decided to analyse people's concerns and appraisals in the situations under study.

For instance, the study on the chinampas found *goal* as one of the concerns. The designer had the *goal* of enjoying an experience in a culturally and environmentally well-preserved setting. This produced an *accomplishment of goals* appraisal, and therefore an emotion of satisfaction.

Desmet's list of 14 product relevant emotions was found useful as a guideline. NG was confused at the beginning because they lacked a list of emotions they could use. Nevertheless, after the initial stages, the designers found Desmet's list to be narrow. They were interested in including more emotions in the study.

III.2 Big Picture versus Detail

The NG found that their model did not offer ways in which designers could understand more thoroughly the process in which emotion is elicited. Some of the comments included:

"There is little explanation on the processes behind emotions. User research is time and resources consuming. When I have time to do it, I want to know exactly what kind of information I should be looking for. I didn't find enough clues and detail as to how the process of eliciting emotion works."

On the other hand, one of the designers in DG stated:

"I found it very useful to know that by studying people's concerns we could have a better understanding of what our designs should be like and why."

Designers in this project found Norman's model to focus on the big picture by including different levels in which emotions occur. On the other hand, Desmet's model offers a more detailed explanation of emotion with the appraisal process. Designers found such detail useful to understand which aspects of the process they should study, including concerns and expectations of people.

III.3 Emotions and Aesthetics at the Visceral Level

Table 3 was presented as a first attempt to visualise similarities between both models. However, it was soon discovered that this match was not so simple. A 'Yes' in the table indicates that the concern is related to the corresponding level. The question mark indicates that the team is not sure whether the concern corresponds to that level.

Table 3. Comparison of Norman's and Desmet's models

Appraisal model	Three levels of emotion model		
Concerns	Visceral	Behavioural	Reflective
Goals		Yes	Yes
Attitudes	Yes	?	Yes
Standards		Yes	Yes
Knowledge and expectations		?	Yes

Norman suggests that the aspect of objects affects the visceral level and can generate an aesthetic experience. Recent research also suggests that aesthetic pleasure can be traced back to the evolution of humans. Hekkert suggests that certain patterns in the environment are considered to be beneficial ‘to our primary’s sense’s functioning’ (Hekkert, 2006, p. 10) and elicit an aesthetic experience just as they elicit an emotion. This idea suggests that there is an aesthetic experience at the emotional/visceral level. However, some authors suggest that an aesthetic experience involves an evaluation of the previous knowledge of the person (Dickie, 1997; Matthews, 1997; McMahon, 1999, 2005).

The researcher agrees that the visceral level assesses whether a stimulus may be harmful or beneficial to the person, which results in an emotion. Nevertheless, it is arguable whether the visceral level can perpetrate an aesthetic reaction. It is normally accepted that aesthetic reaction occurs when the reflective level takes part of the process, and there is no reaction beyond emotion when only the visceral level is at play. This discussion can bring up the following diagram (Figure 3). Further research on the connections between emotion and aesthetic experience in design is necessary.

Figure 3. Appearance of an Object, Emotion and Aesthetic Experience

III.4 Research on Emotion, Concerns, and Appraisals: Investment or Waste of Time?

Some designers found themselves struggling to understand the differences between the different types of concerns. Nevertheless, there were other members that found the categories of concerns useful. The team lacked time to carry out extensive user research that would have provided more thorough information. Most designers admitted that Desmet's model offers the option of developing a better understanding of the user if the

team has the time and resources to develop valid and relevant user research. However, it consumes too much time for application to smaller projects. The team also highlighted the model's limitations for studying interaction with objects.

IV. Conclusions

The results from this Project involve different points that might appear disparate. This is because the main goal of the paper is to report feedback from designers attempting to use the models. The first point in agreement is that theory was useful for addressing a practical project. This paper attempts to raise questions about the theoretical models and their potential use by designers. Hopefully, these questions may be helpful to enrich or modify theoretical models and make them more accessible to the practice of design.

Norman's model offers a broad explanation of emotion and how it occurs at different cognitive levels. It was useful for designers who require a general introduction to emotion. Designers found it helpful for classifying emotions, but not for understanding the emotions studied, in particular the factors that elicited them.

Desmet's model explains in more detail the process by which emotion is elicited. It was The model offers an explanation that designers may use for carrying out more rigorous research on emotion. This suggests that Desmet's model offers designers a tool to develop meaningful concepts related to emotion.

The classification found most useful by designers to start the analysis of a project was that of Norman. However, it proved difficult to define a list of emotions from scratch in NG. This meant that the list of 14 emotions suggested by Desmet was useful as a guideline, but limited in scope because some designers decided to incorporate emotions not included in the list.

Desmet's model offers the starting point to question the validity of basing designs on market segments. This research suggests that designers can go beyond consideration of the concerns their target users share. Designers could explore emotion in order to design for people that share specific concerns, as opposed to design for people that share market

characteristics such as age, income, or education. This uncovers further questions. Can there be 'emotional segments'? Should these market segments be defined by common concerns, therefore creating 'concern segments'?

The comparison of both theories brought up a point deserving further research: the difference between visceral emotional response and aesthetic experience. This paper suggests that an emotional response, as described by Norman, does not imply an aesthetic experience. This statement deserves further investigation, given that current research suggests that there may be an aesthetic experience at the visceral level (Hekkert, 2006). A better understanding of this issue may help designers comprehend whether they want to elicit a particular emotion or an aesthetic experience; or to elicit the first to enrich the latter. For instance, if the designers want to elicit a particular emotion at the visceral level, they can look for elements that bring forth automatic bodily reactions. If they want to elicit an aesthetic experience through emotional reactions, they can investigate concerns and expectations of the users they design for. This second process would elicit emotion at the reflective level.

The discussions during this research involved mainly two of the emotional levels: visceral and reflective. Further research is necessary at the behavioural level. It is suggested that even if the appraisal process were universal, the emotions elicited at the behavioural level vary considerably to the list of 14 emotions suggested by Desmet.

Both models offer a valid and useful framework for designers to address the phenomenon of emotion. However, in design practice, it is essential to use and comprehend different sources and interpret them creatively in order to address the complex world of emotion.

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